

ASPECTS quantum hackathon

Physics Poems

These poems were
written by our hackers,
exclusively using
words extracted from
peer-reviewed physics
journal articles

Facilitated by

Afra Khan

Predictions By Saulo

Interacted in the past
Shown to be

incompatible

Found wanting a grossly
non-local

“hidden variable”!

Individual one-half
particles

Unaffected by the past
Moving freely

It is a matter of
indifference

That creates the
essential difficulty

**Entanglement can not
be created for free**

By Mark Mitchison

A family is unique
It can be manipulated,
But not **created**

For free.

Families are necessary

But are they fixed?

Parties can attach and
will remove

Then the family is

renewed and mixed

Belonging is important

Untitled

By Khalak Mahadeviya

Is World War a
history or
unavoidable?

Not **predictable** or
reversible

Can we discard the
uncertainty by
throwing away
The garbage of
engines and
machinery?

**Reality of the scrambled
by Oisin**

Sometimes an omelette
Results in heart collapse
Just human nature

Untitled
By Srishti Nautigal

Frobenius norm was a major figure in Chemistry
Curious, and precise, always executing experiments at
Hamilton P4Fifty

In contrast was NISQ,
a performer to a fault: erratic and friendly,
outperforming the “leafs” in quick spins
before Hamilton P4Fifty

Frobenius would observe NISQ from the spatial unitary of
Hamilton P4Fifty in curious fashion:

“An **incoherent** one, that one”

“A **distinct** one, that one”

“A **good** one, that one”

Devising a scheme for an encounter, Frobenius ordered an
8-fold symmetric electron-model and diagonalized it
To demonstrate optimal compatibility

But an electron didn't effect NISQ;
Determined to spin fashionably in time
Frobenius returns with a layer model: 58 orbitals this
time

Then a larger one, then larger, performing more
Complicated integrals each time

Then arrived the moment when NISQ stopped spinning

“An **accurate** one, that one”

“A **determined** one, that one”

“a **good** one, that one”

They fell together, those two, in maximum depth of
chemistry and minimal time

They now spin and integrate together,
Often incoherently,
Often erratically,
But always in a grouping;
Without any loss of generality
They spin and solve and solve and spin greatly,
Outside and inside Hamilton P4Fifty

Us
By Shushmi

Family is freedom
Network is interaction
Layers by layers, motivation
inspires us
Constant- depth of light underlies
us
Gravity of complexities weights us
to our ground state
Ideas and inspiration rise us
Emergence of future form
excitations for us
Natural energy represents us
Limits contrast us
Expectation stress us
Architecture of Freedom
To group us
To rise us
Family is freedom
Network is interaction
We discover good us

Unknown by unknown

Current era of **noise**, since
decades ago.
Potential polarised state as
time progresses
Net reactivity to physically
malice
Here, beyond classical path is
proposed
Quantum allows one to
communicate
Breakthroughs to mitigate
errors beyond
Still lacks sufficient
verification
However, optimal path is not
necessary

P
by Artur

The quantum state
Fundamental target
Noisy, unclear,
exponentially

LARGE

Challenge

Asymptotically out of
control goal

Are

We

Not

P?

Smooth Oracular

By Nidhi

Oracular speed up by costa
Dyson is chosen
Homogeneous equation
Solution in particular
Operators with no error
Encoded via **truncation**
Dissipative optimal solution
Discretised differential
equation
Classical time ordering
strategy
Approach simplified oracularly

Unknown by AK

The will to
realise an answer
Challenging
traditional values
Divergences arise
**Alternative ideas
matter!**

Return to equilibrium
By Elsi

We are overwhelmingly rare
They establish
Weak
Inevitably **scattering**

We show so many collisions
They ask
Be **rigorous**
Have strong assumed common

We have no common frequency
They State
Arbitrary conditions
We should be thermalised
But we are different
We approach existence
Through non classical methods
Freedom
Natural interaction
More physical holds
Equilibrium

TES signals

By Grace

Hundreds of **nanoseconds**
Depending on the energy
Characteristics
subsequently recorded
To determine the position
Of **noise** distribution

Experiment conditions
Between detection: optimal
value

Ethernet connection
transfers

Milliseconds counting
Events in real life
Determine discrimination

Entanglement of physics by Unknown

Understanding frequency,
co-ordinates, quantum
equilibrium, and functions
Remains a question
In fact, these terms we
write have **drastic**
Effects on my understanding
of physics
These terms lead to a state
of **frustration**
However these described
terms demonstrate
How the degree of quantum
physics is
Much trickier
Practical applications,
they show to be
Highly successful in my
environment

Identities

By Katie Egan

Is it **family** as suggested
By the name?

Or the degree, the major or the
work

Determining the value
The uniform?

To prove correctness?

To be accepted?

Our systemic group? Our clique?

Our network?

Relationships? The structure of
hierarchy?

Is it what you are given or what
you take?

It is not in the sense that an
identity

Can be **decomposed** and written as
an algorithm

It is a combination, the product
of

The complexity

Unknown

By Ale Summer

Consider A and B
Two distinct but **entangled**
Quantum systems.
Rudimentary approaches fail
To test them faithfully
Exponential scaling prohibits
Their use

And so, it's quantum steering
That comes into play,
It's quantum steering the
Test to address the so
CALLED **SEPARABILITY PROBLEM**
And A and B still entangled
Even if apart?

A variational technique to
Test meaningful connection,
A variational technique
Developed for quantum computers
Quantum steering brings A and B
Back to a single reference system
Will it be enough?

Unknown
By Luca

We will briefly, with our
energy,
Approach with effectiveness
tackle this **trajectory**
With non-zero assuming, we
propose a formulation,
Considerably optimal, without
optimisation
With our effectiveness, our
novel principle,
Will be compelling, without us
mechanical

Our approach has emerged with
motivation
A true, first class method for
quantisation
A new perspective, a big promise
With excellent advantage, and
considerable focus

Unknown By Unknown

When I was a child and
Written on my toys
Was "made in Taiwan"
I never imagined
A Taiwanere Quantum Computing
Research Centre
And Centre for Quantum Technology
While in Bristol
The wills physics laboratory
Is on Tyndall Avenue
Thus named
For the famous Irish educator
physicist scientist
He explaineed the heat
In Earths atmosphere
As capacity of the gases
In air
To absorb infrared radiation
That is
The greenhouse effect
And told us why the sky is blue
Fore father of climate science

Is it possible to read Heisenberg's paper?

By Eoin

Heisenberg's 1925 paper was pure magic,
In deed it is difficult to understand,
And only of historical interest today
He gives remarkably few details of the
calculations

Yet, it is possible to read Heisenberg's
paper;

The incomprehensible breakthrough
Of today's quantum mechanics

“Discard all hope of observing
unobservable quantities
Instead only relations between
observables occur

Transition amplitude
Anharmonic oscillations
Toy systems

Pure magic

And incomprehensible practicality

We are an EU-funded consortium of scientists investigating the thermodynamics of precision measurement using quantum systems. Spanning five European countries, our partners collaborate to identify fundamental limits and reveal new design principles for energy-efficient and precise quantum measuring devices.

The burgeoning quantum technology revolution promises a paradigm shift in the way that we generate, process, and communicate information. Technologies such as quantum computation and quantum sensing are enabled by our ability to control and measure quantum systems with exquisite precision. Such precise measurement and control consume power, meaning that the large-scale deployment of quantum technologies will come at an increasingly large energetic and environmental cost. It is therefore vitally important to develop more energy-efficient devices for precise quantum measurement that can operate at the nanoscale.

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